

ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE FIELD AND ACTUAL STRESS-STRAIN FIELD
IN COMPOSITE PLATE BY MOIRE INTERFEROMETRY*

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ABSTRACT

The actual stress-strain field which results from damage in composites under loading will be obviously different from the ideal stress-strain field in the undamaged composites. Determination of the damage field and the actual stress-strain field is a very important problem for research on strength and failure of composite laminate using experimental technique. Moire interferometry adopted is a whole field optical method with high sensitivity, fringe contrast and spatial resolution. For example, for a cross-ply glass fiber woven/epoxy composite plate under the action of tension, both the damage factor and the actual stress which are the function of the coordinates and the far-field stress has been calculated from the actual strain field measured based on the generalized elastic damage model.

INTRODUCTION

Continuum damage mechanics has been applied to analyse damage in composite materials and some progresses have been made recently [1-7]. For resin-matrix composite such as glass fiber woven/epoxy composite, micro-cracks of matrix take place on a large scale under a low-load level. The damage region will then expand and degree of damage intensify as the applied load increases.

In the laminate there are some damage fields which may produce change of stiffness and redistribution of stress and strain. However, experimental measurement on damage field and further determination of changes on stress field are very important problems for research on the strength and fracture of composite laminates.

The anisotropic damage characters using the coarse moire method (the frequencies of the specimen grating used are 20-50 l/mm) have been measured (6-8). Because of its low-sensitivity, the damage field of the materials could not be detected with sufficient sensitivity and accuracy.

In this paper, moire interferometry [9] that provides whole-field in-plane (u, v) displacement contours is adopted. Its sensitivity is in the subwavelength of a laser beam. High spatial resolution, high fringes contrast, long range and relatively large displacement compared to other optical methods are advantages apart from the sensitivity. The on-axis tensile specimen with a central hole was made from a thin glass fiber woven/epoxy plate. At first, a set of moire patterns was used for the determination of actual strain field. Then the damage field and the actual stress field of a damaged region considered were calculated from the generalized elastic damage theory [6]. Some interesting results are reported in this paper.

* This work supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China under number 1860314 and committee for research and conference grants of the University of Hong Kong.

BASIC PRINCIPLE

The constitutive relation for an element of the anisotropic elastic solid material (such as composite) can be written as

$$\epsilon^e = \tilde{E}^{-1} \sigma \quad (1)$$

where ϵ^e and σ are the actual elastic strain tensor and the stress tensor, respectively. \tilde{E}^{-1} is the damaged compliance tensor for the element considered and changes with the damage of material. Introducing an alternative imaginary stress tensor $\tilde{\sigma}$ and an alternative imaginary strain tensor $\tilde{\epsilon}^e$, Eq. (1) may be expressed alternatively as the following constitutive relation of undamaged material, i.e.

$$\tilde{\epsilon}^e = E^{-1} \tilde{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

where E^{-1} is the compliance tensor of the undamaged material.

It is pointed out that the damaged compliance tensor \tilde{E}^{-1} is the function of the damage factor Δ which can characterize anisotropic property, i.e. $\tilde{E}^{-1} = \tilde{E}^{-1}(\Delta)$ and then the damaged stiffness tensor $\tilde{E} = \tilde{E}(\Delta)$. To satisfy requirements of symmetry for the tensors, some important relations are derived as

$$\epsilon_{ij}^e = \Delta_{ik}^{\frac{1}{2}} \Delta_{lj}^{\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{\epsilon}_{kl}^e \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{E}_{ijmn}^{-1} = \Delta_{ik}^{\frac{1}{2}} \Delta_{lj}^{\frac{1}{2}} \Delta_{mo}^{\frac{1}{2}} \Delta_{pn}^{\frac{1}{2}} E_{klop}^{-1} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{ij} = \tilde{E}_{ijmn} \tilde{\epsilon}_{mn}^e \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is also a symmetric second order tensor and the relation between the damage factor Δ and $\Delta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is

$$\Delta_{ij} = \Delta_{if}^{\frac{1}{2}} \Delta_{fi}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

It is noted that the damage variable tensor D is related to the damage factor tensor Δ , i.e.

$$\Delta_{ij} = (\delta_{ij} - D_{ij})^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where δ_{ij} is Kronecker delta.

It should be emphasized that in the loading process all the tensors are the function of the remote applied stress σ^∞ and the coordinates of the element positions, i.e.

$$\epsilon^e = \epsilon^e(x, y, \sigma^\infty) \quad \sigma = \sigma(x, y, \sigma^\infty)$$

$$\Delta = \Delta(x, y, \sigma^\infty) \quad D = D(x, y, \sigma^\infty)$$

and

$$\tilde{E} = \tilde{E}(x, y, \sigma^\infty) \quad \text{or} \quad \tilde{E}^{-1} = \tilde{E}^{-1}(x, y, \sigma^\infty)$$

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Moire interferometry is used to obtain the in-plane displacement contours relating to the damage field. The specimen is coated with a thin crossed reflective phase grating with lines parallel to the x and y axes. Two collimated coherent beams A and B cross in space at an angle 2α (fig. 1) to produce a virtual grating of frequency

'f' with lines parallel to the x-axis. A second virtual grating with lines parallel to the y-axis can be similarly produced. Before loading the frequency of the specimen grating is $f/2$. When the specimen deforms due to load, the frequency and direction of the specimen grating changes. Moire fringes result from the superposition of

Fig. 1 Experimental schematic.

Fig. 2 Specimen geometry and elements evaluated.

the deformed specimen grating and the virtual reference grating. These fringes depict the u or v isothetics, i.e. contours of displacement component along the x or y directions respectively and are governed by the following equations.

$$u = N_x / f \quad \text{and} \quad v = N_y / f \quad (8)$$

where N_x and N_y are the fringe orders in the u and v patterns respectively.

The strain tensor components can be derived from the displacement fields using the relations

$$\epsilon_{xx} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} ; \quad \epsilon_y = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \quad \text{and} \quad \epsilon_{xy} = \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) / 2 \quad (9)$$

CALCULATION PROCEDURE

The tensile specimen with a central hole (fig. 2) was made from a cross-ply glass fiber woven/epoxy composite plate. The hole was 2 mm in diameter and the specimen width was 20 mm. A 600 lines/mm cross-line grating was transferred around the hole of the specimen. Moire patterns corresponding to the u and v isothetics were recorded at 14 load levels. Representative patterns corresponding to $\sigma^\infty = 31$ MPa (fig. 3 (a) and 3 (b)) and 78 MPa (figs. 3 (c) and 3 (d)) are shown.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 3 Representative moire interferometric patterns
 (a) u-field and (b) v-field corresponding to $\sigma^\infty = 31$ MPa.
 (c) u-field and (d) v-field for $\sigma^\infty = 78$ MPa.

The procedure for evaluating the relative tensors are as follows.

1. For calculating the damage field and the actual stress field as well as their change in the loading process, 10 elements (1×1 mm²) located on either side of the x axis are selected (Fig. 2).

2. Using eqs. (8) and (9), the corresponding components ($\epsilon_{xx}, \epsilon_{yy}, \epsilon_{xy}$) of the actual strain tensor and their principal values (ϵ_1, ϵ_2) for the given elements are calculated from the displacement fields which are obtained by moire interferometry. The components ($\tilde{\epsilon}_{xx}, \tilde{\epsilon}_{yy}, \tilde{\epsilon}_{xy}$) of the imaginary strain tensor may be deduced similarly from the undamaged displacements fields when the damage has not taken place yet.

3. The component values of the tensor Δ_{ij}^1 are determined by substituting ϵ_{ij} and $\tilde{\epsilon}_{ij}$ into eq. (3). Then inserting these values Δ_{ij}^1 into eq. (6), gives the components Δ_{ij}^1 .

4. The component values D_{ij} of the damage variable and their principal values (D_1 and D_2) can be obtained using eq. (7) with the measured Δ_{ij}^1 values.

5. The compliance components E_{ijmn}^{-1} of all the damaged elements may be obtained from eq. (4) [10].

6. Finally, from eq. (5) the actual stress field of the damaged region selected is estimated in the form of $\sigma_{ij}(x, y, \sigma^\infty)$ and their principal values $\sigma_i(x, y, \sigma^\infty)$ can accordingly be evaluated.

CONCLUSIONS

Some interesting conclusions can be made as follows:

(1) The principal values D of six elements near the edge of the hole for nine remote applied load levels are shown in Fig. 4. It is obvious that the values D_1 for every element increases as far-field applied stress σ^∞ (Fig. 4) and that for any one of

Fig. 4 Effect of far field stress on principal damage factor (D_1)

Fig. 5 Effect of element location on principal damage factor (D_1)

remote applied stress σ^∞ , the D_1 decrease with the distance from the hole, i.e. the greater the distance from the hole, the smaller values of D_1 become (Fig. 5). These results appears that damage evolution in the given composite is related to loading and distance.

(2) The elements on both sides of the x-axis have same trend for the damage evolution in the loading process. The quantitative difference of damage evolution along both sides of the x-axis results primarily from the nonhomogeneity of composite plate used.

(3) It has been pointed out that the $\tilde{\sigma}_{11} - \sigma^\infty$ relation would be linear if there is no damage in the material in the whole loading process. For example, the real straight line in Fig. 6 exhibits the $\tilde{\sigma}_{11} - \sigma^\infty$ relation for element No. 5. The three

Fig. 6 Effect of damage on stress distribution around hole.

Fig. 7 Effect of damage on strain distribution around hole.

$\sigma_1 - \sigma^\infty$ curves (corresponding to elements No. 1, 3, 5) display strong nonlinearity. And the difference between σ_1 and $\tilde{\sigma}_1$ increase with the remote applied load for every element.

(4) From Fig. 7, we can show the similarity of the $\epsilon - \sigma^\infty$ relation to the $\sigma - \sigma^\infty$ relation, i.e. the $\epsilon - \sigma^\infty$ relation is also nonlinear.

(5) Finally, we are sure that the sensitivity and the accuracy are sufficient for the determination of the evolution of the damage field as well as the change of actual stress field using the technique of moire interferometry.

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